

Table S1. The GenBank accession numbers of all the 36 chloroplast genome sequences used for phylogenetic analysis.

Order	Species[synonym]	GenBank accession numbers
1	<i>Acaena pinnatifida</i> Ruiz et Pav.	KY419984
2	<i>Agrimonia coreana</i> Nakai	NC_058959
3	<i>Agrimonia coreana</i> Nakai	MW659450
4	<i>Agrimonia nipponica</i> Koidz.	NC_058960
5	<i>Agrimonia nipponica</i> Koidz.	MW659451
6	<i>Agrimonia pilosa</i> Ledeb.	KY419942
7	<i>Argentina phanerophlebia</i> (T.T.Yu et C.L.Li) T.Feng et H. C.Wang	MT114192
8	<i>Cliffortia repens</i> Schltr.	KY419983
9	<i>Hagenia abyssinica</i> (Bruce) J.F.Gmel.	KX008604
10	<i>Hagenia abyssinica</i> (Bruce) J.F.Gmel.	KY420026
11	<i>Leucosidea sericea</i> Eckl. et Zeyh.	KY419929
12	<i>Margyricarpus pinnatus</i> (Lam.) Kuntze	KY419972
13	<i>Polylepis australis</i> Bitter	KY419989
14	<i>Polylepis reticulata</i> Hieron.	KY419921
15	<i>Polylepis</i> sp.	KY419992
16	<i>Potentilla suavis</i> Sojak	MT114190
17	<i>Poterium exstipulata</i> (Svent.) G.J. Zhang comb. nov. [<i>Bencomia exstipulata</i> Svent.]	NC_039924
18	<i>Poterium menendezii</i> (Svent.) Shu.D. Zhang [<i>Dendriopoterium menendezii</i> Svent.]	KY419966
19	<i>Poterium moquiniana</i> (Webb et Berthel.) Shu.D. Zhang [<i>Marcetella moquiniana</i> (Webb et Berthel.) Svent.]	KY420023
20	<i>Poterium sphaerocarpa</i> (Svent.) Shu.D. Zhang [<i>Bencomia sphaerocarpa</i> Svent.]	KY419986
21	<i>Poterium spinosum</i> L. [<i>Sarcopoterium spinosum</i> (L.)	KY419948
22	<i>Rosa multiflora</i> Thunb.	NC_039989
23	<i>Sanguisorba alpina</i> Bunge	ON360976
24	<i>Sanguisorba filiformis</i> (Hook.f.) Hand.-Mazz.	KY419920
25	<i>Sanguisorba filiformis</i> (Hook.f.) Hand.-Mazz.	NC_044693
26	<i>Sanguisorba hakusanensis</i> Makino	NC_056804
27	<i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i> L.	KY419975
28	<i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i> L.	ON360977
29	<i>Sanguisorba stipulata</i> Raf.	NC_044691
30	<i>Sanguisorba tenuifolia</i> Fisch. ex Link var. <i>alba</i> Trautv.et Mey.	NC_044692
31	<i>Sanguisorba tenuifolia</i> Fisch. ex Link var. <i>alba</i> Trautv.et Mey.	ON360978
32	<i>Sanguisorba tenuifolia</i> Fisch. ex Link var. <i>tenuifolia</i>	NC_042223
33	<i>Sanguisorba tenuifolia</i> Fisch. ex Link var. <i>tenuifolia</i>	ON360979
34	<i>Sibbaldia aphanopetala</i> Hand.-Mazz.	MT178810
35	<i>Sibbaldianthe adpressa</i> (Bunge) Juz.	MT114191
36	<i>Spenceria ramalana</i> Trimen	KY419995